

Mathematics education in a context of climate change

Magnus Ödmo, Malmö University, ✉ magnus.odmo@mau.se

The overall goal of the research project presented here is to investigate and produce knowledge about how students and teachers are learning mathematics when presented with mathematics in the context of climate change. In order to address this question, some ethical issues will be taken into account. First, there is a brief overview of different ethical issues concerning the questions, “Is there is an ethical responsibility to bring the concept of climate change into the mathematical learning situation?”. Secondly, I will present the school-based-research. A number of lessons will be created, and an overview of the content of those will be presented here. They will contain, ethical considerations but also mathematical models and different perspectives on climate change, for the students to discuss and engage in.

Ethical responsibility to bring climate change into the mathematical classroom

For this research to be fruitful, some ethical issues will be taken into account. Why should climate change be part of the mathematical curriculum is one of those. Is there even a moral obligation to address these issues, and if the answer is yes, how would this affect the teaching and learning? Abtahi et al. (2017) address the question “how incorporating issues of climate change into the teaching and learning of mathematics can be understood as a moral and ethical act.”. They conclude that although including climate change in mathematics classrooms can be viewed as an ethical or moral responsibility of mathematics teachers, in their day-today practice their decisions about issues are complex. These ethical challenges relate to, for example, the degree of involvement and interest of students in the issue of climate change, the possible discomfort of students, the uncertainty of how to respond, the unclear path of any possible contributions of their actions to the wider society, and finally a more general sense of dealing with the unknown. Teachers face practical obstacles in incorporating issues related to climate change in their mathematics classrooms, such as “lack of resources, lack of sources of data related to their immediate community, lack of curriculum mandates, and lack of time” (p. 11).

Karrow, Khan & Fleener (2017) also discuss mathematics education’s ethical relation with the climate change. They argue that mathematics education is skewed towards economic interests instead of ethical relations. According to them mathematics education must move away from preoccupation with economics to one found by virtue ethics. In reviewing a

Please cite as: Ödmo, M. (2021). Mathematics education in a context of climate change. In D. Kolloosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 211–214). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5392572>

number of papers, they conclude that the current mathematics education is formed through the prism of economy, instead they suggest a mathematics education that concerns the development of the individual in relation with our Planets Ecosystem. To do this they suggest moving mathematics more into the realm of nature. For instance, recursive mathematics which can describe the reproduction of rabbits or formation of flower leaves. Fractals, complex systems and uncertainty are other areas that can be found in this mathematics of nature. This suggests a new epistemology, where learning is not an acquisition and accumulation of knowledge but rather a process of engagement with an understanding that all knowledge is uncertain and situated. This is also in line with UNESCOs slogan “changing minds not the climate” UNESCO (n.d.).

Perspectives on climate change

The teaching and learning in a context of climate change also involves a personal viewpoint towards the issue of climate change which is elaborated in several papers. How do we view ourselves in relation to the world, climate change and the dystopian future that is presented to us? Drawing on the notion of the *Anthropocene* which signals the shift from solving a problem to learning to live with a problem, Coles (2017) suggests the concept of *habit* that allow us to conceptualize ourselves in the world around us. Moving away from a savior narrative, *habit* will help people to connect individual and global perspectives. This issue is also discussed by Latour (2018) where he suggests a perspective of the *critical zone* to deal with the climate change. He argues that the scientific notion of us being ON the blue planet, leads us to take the role of savior instead we must face the reality of the critical zone in which we all are in some sense part of and trapped in. (Mikulan & Sinclair, 2017) draws on the notion of the *Anthropocene* claiming that we need to think in a more non-human way where the human is not the center of everything. They also show in their paper why mathematics is well suited for this endeavor. The above-mentioned examples are all ethical considerations for a teacher going into the mathematical learning situation, they all based on different ethical assumptions, and these will be investigated and analyzed in the research.

School-based-research in the mathematical learning situation

In my coming school-based-research, I will create several lessons that will touch on the different aspects of climate change. In the classroom there will be discussions about ethical considerations concerning climate change. Different ethical standpoints and perspectives will be presented to the students, illustrating the complexity of the problem. Articles dealing with the ethical implications concerning climate change are multiple in the research community. Gardiner (2011) argues climate change plays a fundamental role due to decision making, which effect animal and future generations. They also point out some reasons for why it is hard to be ethically sound. Local emissions have a global effect. A decision in one place may have implications in a totally different place in the world. Raymond (2004) argues for an ethics of commons. The atmosphere is a global common good and he proposes that

the emissions should be allocated between nations. It could be done by using the principle of equal burden. Meaning that nations should reduce their emissions based on the burden of this reduction. Another approach based on equal human rights would be to allow an emission level per capita. Shue (1999) concludes that “whatever needs to be done by wealthy industrialized states or by poor non-industrialized states about global environmental problems, the costs should initially be borne by the wealthy industrialized states” (p.111). He then describes the reasoning behind this conclusion and how proportional and progressive burden can be explained. All these suggestions, mentioned above, are based on different ethical assumptions and are examples of what can be presented and discussed in the classroom. They also deal with mathematical concepts, for instance proportionality and progression, that can be used as examples in the mathematical classroom.

When we say *climate change* what type of perspective and understanding are we referring to? Are there other models and perspectives that can be used to understand and explain the climate crisis and the world we live in? Huneman & Lemoine (2014) explore interesting distinctions of modeling. “Modeling can be seen in terms of representing a target system. Other epistemic functions, such as producing data or detecting phenomena, are at least as relevant” (p. 3). Other useful distinctions can be made, for instance between phenomenological and mechanistic models (p. 3). There are distinctions that can be applied to the different models of climate change as well. And relevant questions of which type of model to use in the classroom emerges. We may also ask ourselves if alternative models can bring light into the classroom concerning the climate crisis? Dutreuil (2014) investigates the epistemology of computational models that stem from an analysis of the Gaïa Hypothesis. The model has been criticized for being too abstract, describing fictive daisies on an imaginary planet, and trying to answer *what-if* questions, “how would a planet look like if life had no influence on it?”. For these reasons the model has been considered not testable and therefore not legitimate in science, and in any case not very interesting since it explores non-actual issues. “This criticism implicitly assumes that science should only be involved in the making of models that are *actual*, by opposition to *what-if*, and *specific*, by opposition to *abstract*.” Dutreuil (2014, p. 2). This research aims to challenge these criticisms and use the mathematical approach to illustrate how one can make a theoretical model first, without any empirical data and then see what understanding it will bring to the students. As an example, imaginary numbers were conceived long before there was any practical use for them. Several centuries later it was obvious that they were very practical tool to use in electrical engineering. A similar approach can be made to use an abstract mathematical model of the earth. And in this way remove a lot of variables, in doing so creating a new learning situation and a way to gain knowledge of how students learn mathematics in this context.

Analysis of data

In my analysis of the data from the classroom, I will use *actor-network-theory* (ANT). It is a methodological approach to study social phenomena where everything exists in a continuously changing network of relationships Latour (2005). As Latour (2005) describes,

everything that happens in a social situation takes place on the same level. So, for instance humans as well as objects have agency, and both play a role in creating a social situation. In ANT there are two main concepts, *mediators* and *intermediaries*. *Mediators* “transform, translate, distort, and modify the meaning or the elements they are supposed to carry”. (Latour, 2005, p. 39). *Intermediaries* on the other hand, is what transports meaning without transformation: “defining its inputs is enough to define its outputs” (p. 39). But how do we distinguish between mediators and intermediaries? Latour mentions that to learn ANT is nothing more than to “become sensitive to the differences in the literary, scientific, moral, political, and empirical dimensions of the two types of accounts” (p. 109).

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my special thanks of gratitude to my supervisors, Anna Chronaki and Lisa Björklund Boistrup, for their support in writing this presentation.

References

- Abtahi, Y., Gøtze, P., Steffensen, L., Hauge, K. H., & Barwell, R. (2017). Teaching climate change in mathematics classroom: An ethical responsibility. *Philosophy of Mathematics Education Journal*, 32.
- Coles, A. (2017). Habits and binds of mathematics education in the anthropocene. *Philosophy of Mathematics Education Journal*, 32.
- Dutreuil, S. (2014). What good are abstract and what-if models? Lessons from the Gaïa hypothesis. *History and Philosophy of the Life Sciences*, 36(1), 16–41.
- Shue, H. (1999). Global environment and international inequality. *International Affairs (Royal Institute of International Affairs 1944-)*, 75(3), 531–545. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2623635>
- Gardiner, S. M. (2011). *A perfect moral storm: The ethical tragedy of climate change*. Oxford University Press.
- Huneman, P & Lemoine, M. (2014). Introduction: The plurality of modeling. *History and Philosophy of the Life Sciences*, 36(1), 5–15.
- Karrow, D., Khan, S., & Fleener, J. (2017). Mathematics education’s ethical relation with and response to climate change. *Philosophy of Mathematics Education Journal*, 32.
- Latour, B. (2018). *Down to earth: Politics in the new climatic regime*. Polity Press.
- Latour, B. (2005) *Re-assembling the social: An introduction to actor-network theory*. Oxford University Press.
- Mikulan, P., & Sinclair, N. (2017). Thinking mathematics pedagogy stratigraphically in the anthropocene. *Philosophy of Mathematics Education Journal*, 32.
- Raymond, L. (2004). Cutting the “Gordian knot” in climate change policy. *Energy Policy*, 34(6), 655–658.
- UNESCO (n. d.) *Preparation of a declaration on ethical principles in relation to climate change*. www.unesco.org/new/en/social-and-human-sciences/themes/comest/ethical-principles